

Review

The Therapeutic Potential of Phytotherapy: A Review of Efficacy, Cultural Value, and Challenges for Integration into Contemporary Healthcare.

Emilia Simões Calçada^{1*} .

¹ ABS – Atlântico Business School, Vila Nova de Gaia, Porto, Portugal;

² IPB – Polytechnic Institute of Bragança, Bragança, Portugal.

* Correspondence: ema.fsc@gmail.com

Abstract

Phytotherapy, one of the therapeutic modalities of Traditional Chinese Medicine (TCM), has gained significant prominence as a complementary therapeutic practice, being utilised in domestic settings and formal contexts such as healthcare services. Its therapeutic potential, demonstrated across various clinical conditions, has sparked interest and necessitated an analysis of its contribution to human health. Therefore, the aim of this study is to identify and discuss the benefits of phytotherapy for human health and to analyse the challenges associated with its integration into healthcare services.

This is a Narrative Literature Review (NLR), which incorporates 12 articles published between 2014 and 2025 and searched in PubMed and LILACS. The results revealed that phytotherapy is used across different populations (children, the elderly and even pregnant women) and for multiple clinical conditions, such as Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus (T2DM), gastrointestinal disorders, bronchitis, and breast cancer. The main motivational factors for its use include accessibility, low cost, cultural tradition, and the perception of safety. However, some gaps are notable concerning standardisation, safety, the quality of clinical trials, and communication between practitioners and patients. It is concluded that phytotherapy presents high therapeutic potential and cultural acceptance, and can complement conventional therapy. Nevertheless, its full integration into health systems requires more studies, regulation of its use, professional training, and the promotion of safe, evidence-based practices.

Citation: Calçada E.S., dos Santos L.S. Phytotherapy for Anxiety: The Therapeutic Potential of Phytotherapy: A Review of Efficacy, Cultural Value, and Challenges for Integration into Contemporary Healthcare. *Journal of Complementary Therapies in Health*. 2026;4(1) 10.5281/zenodo.17871129

Academic Editor: Jorge Rodrigues

Received: 22 October 2025

Reviewed: 19 November 2025

Revised: 30 November 2025

Accepted: 5 December 2025

Published: 9 December 2025

Keywords: Phytotherapy; Traditional Chinese Medicine; Primary Healthcare Integration; Clinical Efficacy; Safety and Regulation; Cultural Value; Health Professional Training.

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1. Introduction

Chinese phytotherapy is one of the pillars of TCM, and can be explained as an ancient therapeutic approach that uses plants and natural substances to promote health and treat various diseases. Over more than 4,000 years, this system has been refined and validated not only by tradition but also by recent studies, highlighting phytotherapy as a significant complementary alternative within the current context of integrative health ^{1,2}.

The therapeutic approach of phytotherapy is based on the philosophical principles of *Yin-Yang*, the Five Phases (or Five Movements), and the circulation of *Qi* (vital energy). This philosophy guides the selection and combination of medicinal plants, aiming not only to resolve immediate symptoms but also to restore the body's internal balance ^{3,4}.

In the literature on the subject, it is noted that phytotherapy contributes to human health in various pathological situations, such as in the control of metabolic syndrome^{5,6}, inflammatory disorders⁷ and as support for oncological treatment⁸.

Given that phytotherapy has gained more prominence and that it is important to inform the public, both academic and non-academic, of its multiple health benefits, this article is an NLR that seeks to identify the benefits of phytotherapy for human health, analysing its integration into healthcare and public health strategies.

2. Traditional Chinese Medicine

It can be said that TCM's main concept is holism, based on original theories regarding aetiology, diagnosis, and treatment⁹. It encompasses the signs and symptoms of the entire organism, including the organs, channels and collaterals, *Qi*, blood (*Xue*), and *Yin-Yang*⁹.

Qi can be explained as the energy that manifests physically and spiritually, capable of passing through various states of aggregation¹⁰, and is re-established through the balance of the opposing forces of *Yin* and *Yang*, which manifest in the body as heat and cold, internal and external, and deficiency and excess¹¹. *Yin* and *Yang* symbolise opposing forces, where *Yin* represents the shaded side of the mountain—the dark, feminine, and negative forces, and *Yang* represents the sunny side of the mountain, the illuminated, masculine, and positive forces^{4,11}.

TCM postulates that for balance to exist, *Yin-Yang* must be present, being responsible for the changes in the body that will restore balance^{4,12}. Regarding diagnosis in TCM, it is carried out through a holistic and detailed approach, so that Chinese medicine, although difficult to practise, arrives at a more certain and more complete diagnosis, a diagnosis that incorporates all aspects of the patient's life, thus leading to a safer treatment than Western medicine¹³.

This allows for the assessment of the body's energetic and functional state, not only for the purpose of identifying the disease but also to understand the internal imbalance that triggered its onset. According to Maciocia¹³, this is based on the idea that there must be a fundamental *Yin* and *Yang* imbalance for illness to occur, and that this imbalance manifests in all areas of human experience. For example, the patient will show an imbalance in colour, movement, skin texture, food preferences, music, clothing, sports, or painting style. In the body, the channels, the Elements, the Blood, and the entire pathway through which the *Qi* flows will be influenced by the imbalance.

Therefore, the four diagnostic methods in TCM are: Observation; Inquiry; Palpation; and Auscultation and Olfaction¹³.

3. Phytotherapy

Phytotherapy, as a therapeutic technique of TCM, stands out for the use of medicinal plants and minerals, aiming to re-establish the body's energetic balance, as well as to treat the patterns of imbalance diagnosed in light of TCM principles. This branch of TCM studies medicinal plants, their properties, their advantages, their toxicity, and their mode of action, using plants for the treatment of deficiency or excess⁴.

Based on an ancient, holistic philosophy, phytotherapy is a practice that considers the symptoms and causes of illnesses, promoting physical, emotional, and spiritual well-being. It conceives of the individual as a whole, considering physical, emotional, mental, and spiritual aspects of health, seeking to balance and harmonise the organism to promote an optimal state of health¹⁴⁻¹⁸.

In this sense, TCM categorised medicinal plants according to their own energetic principles, where the therapist prescribes single herbs or compound formulas according to the energetic patterns (syndromes) presented by each patient. Therefore, phytotherapy is used complementary to Western medicine or integrated into traditional and cultural medical systems, gaining increasing numbers of followers who seek a natural and holistic approach to health and who are interested in the sustainable use of plant resources¹⁴⁻¹⁶.

3.1. A Brief Historical Note on the Use of Medicinal Plants

Etymologically, the word phytotherapy derives from the Greek words *therapeia*, meaning treatment, and *phyton*, meaning plant; thus, phytotherapy (or therapy by plants) is dedicated to the study of medicinal plants, their chemical compositions, and therapeutic properties¹⁹.

The use of medicinal plants dates back to the earliest civilisations, with archaeological records proving their use since approximately 60,000 years ago. In China, ginseng was used by emperors for more than 3,000 years, and in ancient Egypt, papyri such as the Ebers Papyrus showed the cataloguing of hundreds of species and therapeutic recipes²⁰⁻²³.

Phytotherapy remains, even today, one of the main and oldest disciplines of TCM and is widely used in China and worldwide²⁴, having evolved through the integration of modern scientific methods that have validated the traditional uses of plants, where clinical studies, laboratory research, and government regulations have contributed to its recognition as a legitimate and effective practice²⁵.

3.2. Popular, Traditional, and Scientific Phytotherapy

In the literature on phytotherapy, terms such as popular phytotherapy, traditional phytotherapy, and scientific phytotherapy appear. It is considered important, within the scope of this work, to briefly clarify these concepts. What mainly differentiates these herbal therapies is the method of use, the validation, and the basis of knowledge about medicinal plants^{26,27}.

Popular phytotherapy can be defined as the tradition of domestic and community use of medicinal plants, transmitted orally in each local reality, from generation to generation. This popular wisdom, besides being a strategic source of 'clues' regarding the efficacy or toxicity of medicinal plants to inspire subsequent scientific studies, which then multiply in universities and the pharmaceutical market, constitutes, above all, an important cultural and civic contribution, and, no less importantly, a political one²⁸.

Traditional phytotherapy, most often, relies on written records of its practice, which, depending on its origin, has existed for decades, centuries, or even millennia. But what truly delimits it as a matrix for phytotherapy, in our view, would be the fact that it is not practised in isolation, as a simple therapeutic resource or method, but is always 'coupled' to a context, as an integral part of 'medical systems' originating from peculiar cultures, within the context of a 'field of health knowledge and practice', recognised by the World Health Organization (WHO) as 'traditional medicine'²⁸⁻³¹.

Scientific phytotherapy, in turn, consists of the integrated study of the clinical use of medicinal plants and herbal products for therapeutic, diagnostic, or prophylactic purposes, based on scientific data and evidence, even if initially drawn from popular and traditional knowledge²⁸.

3.3. Its Integration into the Healthcare System

Mendes³² draws attention to a particularly important aspect, and, relying on various authors, state that in China, where phytotherapy originates and is widely used, approximately 30 to 50% of the population has already used herbal products, and in Europe and North America, 50% of the population has used them. Statistics also show that approximately 80% of the world population perceives phytotherapy as their primary health system, especially in developing countries, and that it has been increasingly used in developed countries, demonstrating the importance and, consequently, the need for herbal products to be studied and consciously prescribed so that they are used safely³² and integrated into healthcare services.

Regarding the integration of phytotherapy into healthcare, several studies address the issue. Filho *et al.*³³, referring to the Brazilian context, stress the importance of regulating the use of medicinal plants and herbal products in the national policy on integrative and complementary practices and the national policy on medicinal plants and herbal

products. The country already has initiatives such as *Farmácia Viva* (Living Pharmacy), the National List of Essential Medicines, and the List of Medicinal Plants of Interest to the unified health system. Despite policies that promote the integration of herbal products and their safe use, many practitioners still do not feel confident prescribing them, highlighting the need for training to be better equipped³³.

In the same line, Silva *et al.*³⁴, in their Systematic Literature Review (SLR) on the challenges and strategies for the insertion of phytotherapy into Primary Care, report critical barriers in areas such as insufficient practitioner training, structural and political limitations, a lack of robust clinical evidence, restricted access to inputs, challenges in intersectoral partnerships, and cultural resistance. Therefore, the authors reinforced the need for greater alignment between guidelines and the daily practices of the health system.

By integrating herbal products into healthcare, a significant advance is made in promoting integrative and complementary practices, contributing to a healthcare system that provides effective and culturally relevant therapeutic alternatives³³, making the importance of herbal products for the population using the health system visible³⁵. However, it is understood that for the integration of phytotherapy into healthcare, it is essential that the services employ a phytotherapist (herbal medicine practitioner), who, according to Article 4 of Ordinance No. 207-E/2014, of 8 October³⁶, states that the phytotherapist should be capable of: promoting health and preventing illness, assessing the client's state of health, as well as identifying patterns of imbalance and applying specific criteria of phytotherapy; recognising the limits of their practice, identifying situations that may require referral to other professionals; drawing up the therapeutic plan, defining principles and strategies; prescribing and administering medicinal plants, formulas, supplements, and advising on nutrition, dietetics, and lifestyle; recognising and intervening in adverse reactions; conducting an individualised analysis, investigating personal factors that influence health and well-being; educating for health, informing clients and the public to promote healthy habits and prevent diseases; applying therapeutic methods specific to phytotherapy and correctly identifying the properties of the plants; providing follow-up and monitoring progress, tracking results and adjusting treatment as necessary; establishing a therapeutic relationship; critically evaluating practice, reflecting, analysing cases, gathering feedback, and participating in audits; prioritising scientific integration, keeping up with the literature and applying new knowledge in practice; considering the individual as a whole, and not just isolated symptoms; recognising signs of dysfunction and developing appropriate strategies; prioritising continuous updating and permanent professional development; collecting, interpreting fundamental data and clinical decisions; preparing and presenting case studies; guiding colleagues and interns.

3.4. Legislation on Phytotherapy

In the scope of legislation on phytotherapy, four documents can be highlighted: Law No. 45/2003, of 22 August (The Framework Law for Non-Conventional Therapies); Law No. 71/2012, of 22 August; Ordinance No. 207-E/2014, of 8 October²⁸; and Ordinance No. 172-B/2015, of 5 June³⁷.

Law No. 45/2003 establishes the framework for the activity and practice of practitioners who apply non-conventional therapies (Article 1), recognising phytotherapy as a non-conventional therapy (Article 3). Furthermore, according to this law, the practice of non-conventional therapies can only be carried out by practitioners holding the legally required qualifications and duly accredited for their practice (Article 10)³⁸.

Law No. 71/2012 regulates Law No. 45/2003 regarding the professional practice of applying non-conventional therapies, which includes phytotherapy (Article 2). To perform the function of a non-conventional therapist, one must hold a degree in one of the areas (Article 5), as well as possess the professional card issued by the Central Administration of the Health System (ACSS) (Article 6)³⁹.

With regard to the profession of phytotherapist exclusively, Ordinance No. 207-E/2014, of 8 October, states that phytotherapy is practised under the professional title of phytotherapist (Article 3), who must have knowledge of (Article 4) ³⁶:

- The specific theoretical foundations underpinning their diagnosis and therapeutic intervention;
- The indications and contraindications of phytotherapeutic treatment;
- The theory, practice, and principles of phytotherapy, demonstrating this through various approaches, selecting natural agents, techniques and procedures, or modifying treatment plans to meet the needs of people;
- Interpersonal communication, allowing for an adequate collection of relevant personal and family facts for the application of the therapy, the maintenance of a good relationship with clients, colleagues, and others related to the profession, and the prevention and resolution of conflict situations;
- Psychology and social determinants of health, enabling them to contextualise the therapeutic decision and the care to be provided;
- Behavioural sciences, allowing for appropriate and effective advice on healthy lifestyles;
- Physiology, pathology, pathophysiology, observation of signs and symptoms to identify situations where the person may need the intervention of another health professional.

Finally, in section three of Article 4, the principles of conduct by which the phytotherapist must be governed are set out, namely ³⁶:

- Adopting ethical conduct aimed at guaranteeing the quality of the provision of phytotherapy care;
- Basing the relationship with the client on trust and information, knowing how to communicate effectively to build and maintain a therapeutic relationship;
- Not deliberately causing harm or prejudicing the client, under any circumstances, within the scope of their profession;
- Referring the client, whenever necessary, to the health professional best qualified to treat their health condition;
- Not creating false expectations regarding the expected results of the treatment;
- Not treating people with conditions that are not susceptible to any improvement in their health status through phytotherapy;
- Applying only treatments useful and necessary for the maintenance or recovery of the person's health;
- Developing a treatment plan that involves the active and consented participation of the client, stating the prognosis, the results to be achieved, the therapeutic methods and techniques used, and the regular evaluation of their progress;
- Providing high-quality phytotherapy care, always ensuring client safety;
- Ensuring the confidentiality of health information, as well as secrecy, in accordance with legal norms;
- Accepting multiculturalism, without compromising respect for the principle of non-discrimination of patients, namely based on ancestry, sex, race, language, territory of origin, religion, political or ideological convictions, education, economic situation, social status, or sexual orientation;
- Being available to participate in training in the field of phytotherapy, namely by welcoming students and interns;
- Ensuring the timeliness, quality, rigour, and humanisation of phytotherapeutic healthcare;
- Ensuring the preparation and permanent updating of health information, and registering the treatments performed;

- Ensuring professional development through continuous training.

Ordinance No. 172-B/2015, of 5 June, regulates the general requirements that must be met by the study cycle leading to the Bachelor's degree in Phytotherapy, which is taught in polytechnic institutes, non-integrated polytechnic higher education schools, or polytechnic higher education schools integrated into a university (Article 3). The main components of training are fundamental sciences, clinical sciences and techniques, the principles of phytotherapy, and the practice of phytotherapy³⁷.

4. Methodology

For the implementation of the study, the NLR was adopted as the methodology—a vital part of most empirical articles, dissertations, and funding proposals, performing a vital scientific function⁴⁰. The narrative review is an "older" format (compared to the SLR) and allows for an analysis of the available literature on a subject of interest. As it is not systematic, there are no formal guidelines regarding its completion⁴¹. Even without guidelines and protocols for the NLR, in this specific case, the research question was designed using the PICO acronym: **P**atient – patients; **I**ntervention – phytotherapy; **C**omparison – conventional medicine; **O**utcome (expected results) – therapeutic benefits of phytotherapy for human health. Given this, the question to be answered is: What are the benefits of phytotherapy for human health?

4.1. Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

The inclusion and exclusion criteria are an important aid in the selection of the scientific evidence that will constitute the study sample. Thus, the inclusion criteria are: articles published between 2014–2025; full and free access; publications in English and Portuguese; articles that address the benefits of phytotherapy for human health. The exclusion criteria are: articles published before 2014; without full and free access; languages other than those mentioned; articles focusing on a therapeutic practice other than phytotherapy.

4.2. Explanation of the Search Method

Before proceeding to search for articles in databases, the Health Sciences Descriptors (DeCS) were searched, and three were selected: fitoterapia / phytotherapy; saúde humana / human health; atenção à saúde / delivery of health care. Subsequently, using Boolean operators, the following search phrase was formulated: fitoterapia AND saúde humana AND atenção à saúde (phytotherapy AND human health AND healthcare). The search for evidence was carried out in the PubMed and LILACS databases.

5. Results

This NLR includes 12 studies published between 2016 and 2025 that address the use and benefits of phytotherapy in various areas and diseases, as well as its integration into Primary Care (themes that emerged during the reading and analysis of the articles). Table 1 presents the synthesis of the results and their categorisation by themes/subjects.

Table 1. Synthesis and Categorisation of Scientific Evidence

Ref.	Field	Results	Conclusion
42	Paediatrics	- Origin and transmission of knowledge: the use of phytotherapy is a family legacy, passed down from generation to generation, mainly through oral transmission; - Frequency of use: 96% of respondents reported having used some phytotherapy resource for children and/or adolescents; - Most mentioned plants: fennel (sweet herb), boldo, mint, pineapple, citronella, garlic, lemon grass, ginger, etc.; - Indications: cough,	- The practice of phytotherapy in paediatrics in primary care is a culturally embedded practice, part of the family and community legacy, incorporating traditional knowledge and everyday experiences; - Rescuing and considering this tradition gives new meaning to healthcare, as it allows popular practices to be valued, integrated into the care system,

	<p>abdominal pain, colic, calming effect, expectorant; fever, sore throat, ear and headache, diarrhoea, infections, deworming, and oral hygiene; - Motivation for use: easy access to the plant, high cost of conventional treatments, difficulty accessing medical services, belief in the power of plants as a therapy; - Meanings attributed to phytotherapy beyond cure/treatment: prevention of worsening, recovery of memories and experiences, integration with nature, social aggregation (strengthening community/family ties); - Perception of efficacy: of the 96%, some considered it always efficient and others sometimes efficient.</p>	<p>stimulating autonomy, community participation, and the rational use of medicinal plants.</p>
43	<p>Maternal and Child Health</p> <p>- Statistically significant associations: topical use of almond oil associated with preterm birth; oral use of raspberry leaf associated with a higher probability of Caesarean section; intensive use of liquorice associated with early preterm birth; use of African herbal medicine called <i>mwanaaphopo</i> associated with maternal morbidity and neonatal morbidity or mortality; - 14 studies reported no adverse effects.</p>	<p>- There is not enough strong evidence to guarantee the safety of using many herbal products during pregnancy or postnatally; - There are major gaps in the studies, in terms of variability in doses, pharmaceutical forms, lack of follow-up for adverse events, and the underreporting of events.</p>
44	<p>Maternal and Child Health</p> <p>- Knowledge: 66.2% of pregnant women had a good level of knowledge about phytotherapy; - Attitude: 71.2% showed a positive attitude towards the use of medicinal herbs; - Use outside of pregnancy: 56.5% have used medicinal herbs at some point in their lives; - Use in current pregnancy: 40% used it during pregnancy; - Use in previous pregnancies: 16% confirmed using herbal products in previous pregnancies; - Time of use: many started using it at the beginning of the first trimester; - Motivations: tradition/culture, low cost, easy access, belief that they are natural and safe; - Perceptions of risk: some women considered potential dangers (lack of correct dose, risk of excess), but many believed that, being natural, they would be harmless; - Statistical associations: only marital status showed a significant association with the level of knowledge, while age, education, and occupation did not show a relevant association.</p>	<p>- Most pregnant women in Nsukka who participated in the study had good knowledge and a positive attitude towards the use of phytotherapy; - Effective use during pregnancy was not universal; many women used phytotherapy outside of pregnancy or had used it in previous pregnancies, and a smaller percentage used it currently; - It is recommended that health professionals incorporate guidance on phytotherapy in antenatal care, with specific education to fill knowledge gaps, and that there is open communication with pregnant women about the use of these products.</p>
45	<p>Gastrointestinal Disorders</p> <p>- FGID emerge as one of the most important indications for phytotherapy, given the number of plants used, the accumulated evidence, and the tradition in Europe and beyond; - Plants used in FGID are classified according to their main mechanism or effect: bitters - plants that stimulate gastric secretions; aromatics - plants with essential oils, carminative, that combat spasms; bitter-aromatics - combination of both properties; antispasmodic or carminative plants (essential oils or antispasmodic alkaloids) to relieve colic, distension, gas; mucilaginous plants that soothe or protect the gastrointestinal mucosa; flavonoid-rich plants with anti-inflammatory properties; - Use of plant combinations to increase efficacy or specificity of effect, such as STW</p>	<p>- Phytotherapy, particularly through herbal and combined preparations, is a valid therapeutic option for FGID, even according to the standards of Evidence-Based Medicine; - Well-studied preparations like STW 5 are examples of how this integration can work; - Some gaps still exist, such as: the need for more solid clinical studies for various plants, better safety data, clear mechanisms, standardisation of preparations (dosage, quality, composition); - The use of phytotherapy in FGID is not merely traditional or an alternative, and can be rationally integrated into conventional therapies, when properly studied and practised by qualified practitioners.</p>

		5; - Although there is a long tradition of use, the variation in the quality of evidence for different plants and combinations is notable.	
46	Bronchitis	- Facilitators to the use of phytotherapy: concern about antibiotic resistance, perception that herbal products may be less invasive or cause fewer side effects, relatively easy access, patients' willingness to try alternatives; - Barriers to use: doubts about efficacy compared to antibiotics, concerns about interactions with conventional medicines (safety and adverse effects), cost, taste/flavour; - Conditions for acceptance: reliable evidence, trust, need for guidance.	- Many patients and health professionals consider the use of phytotherapy for acute bronchitis to be acceptable, especially as an alternative to antibiotics, as there is reliable evidence and clinical guidelines supporting its use; - Phytotherapy can help with self-care, reduce unnecessary antibiotic use, and decrease antimicrobial resistance, provided it is used safely; - There is a need for more studies, preparation of local guidelines, and clarification of doses and preparations.
47	Breast Cancer	- Considerable adherence of participants to alternative therapies was observed, with emphasis on phytotherapy (highest prevalence); - Motivational factors: psycho-biological (seeking relief from physical side effects or unpleasant symptoms, improved bodily well-being), psycho-spiritual (faith, spiritual or transcendental dimensions that help face the disease), psycho-social (social support, cultural influence/tradition, desire for personal control over one's own health, popular knowledge).	- Patients with a history of breast cancer demonstrate increased motivation to seek alternative therapies, aiming to improve their quality of life in the face of adverse effects of conventional treatment; - Phytotherapy is the most used alternative therapy by this group of patients; - There is a need for health professionals to be better prepared to provide guidance on these practices, aiming for greater safety, comprehensive and knowledge-based use, reducing the risks of empirical use.
48	Diabetes	- <i>Nigella sativa</i> and fenugreek showed consistent beneficial effects on improving glycaemic control and lipid profile; - Ginger regulates enzymes involved in carbohydrate metabolism; - Curcumin demonstrated the ability to control glucose and lipids through its antioxidant effects, although there are challenges with bioavailability (how much curcumin actually reaches the tissues); - Cinnamon improves glucose transport and inhibits specific enzymes related to glucose metabolism; - <i>Nigella sativa</i> presented the most consistent effects of improvement across the various studies.	- The herbs examined have therapeutic potential and can be used in complementary treatments for T2DM, mainly in glycaemic control and improvement of the lipid profile; - The need for more studies, standardisation in doses and preparations, duration of use, and drug interactions is confirmed.
49	Diabetes	- High prevalence of phytotherapy use among participants; - Significant associations: educational level; socioeconomic level; place of residence; duration of T2DM; - Independent factors associated with the use of phytotherapy: age between 51 and 60 years.	- Patients with T2DM frequently resort to phytotherapy as an anti-diabetic therapy. Factors such as age between 51 and 60 years, low educational level, low socioeconomic level, and average duration of diabetes are associated with this use. It is necessary to evaluate the efficacy and adverse effects of phytotherapy in the treatment of this disease.
50	Diabetes	- Use of herbal products: 68% of patients use herbal products, the most common being: cinnamon, ginger, and fenugreek; - Sources of information: most patients obtained information about herbal products from family, friends, and social media; - Communication with doctors: 71.4% of patients did not inform their doctors	- The use of herbal products is common among patients with T2DM; - There is a patient-doctor communication failure regarding the use of herbal products; - Greater awareness and dialogue about the use of

		about the use of herbal products; - Patients' perceptions: 54% believe that herbal products are effective in controlling T2DM and 46% consider herbal products safe; - Doctors' perceptions: 66% routinely ask patients about the use of herbal products and 25% have a positive opinion about the use of herbal products in T2DM; some doctors expressed concerns regarding the safety and efficacy of herbal products.	herbal products need to be promoted to ensure safety and efficacy in the treatment of T2DM.
51	Integration into Primary Care	- Facilitators: cultural acceptance of phytotherapy in the community, availability of local medicinal plants, previous experience of health professionals with phytotherapy; - Barriers: lack of formal training and knowledge about phytotherapy, concerns about the safety and efficacy of herbal products, and lack of regulation and standards for the clinical use of phytotherapy.	- Although phytotherapy is widely used and culturally accepted in Ghana, there are several challenges to its integration into formal clinical practice; - Adequate training for health professionals and clear regulations for the safe and effective use of phytotherapy need to be developed.
52	Elderly Population	- The main plants used are (from most to least used): mint, chamomile, rue, matico, plantain, boldo, melissa, pennyroyal, paico, and lemon verbena; - Reasons for use: gastrointestinal, nervous, dermal, respiratory, metabolic, and genitourinary problems; - Acquisition methods: home cultivation was the most reported; - Forms of preparation: infusion was the most popular form; - Drug interactions: some plants mentioned have potential interactions that have already been described.	- The use of medicinal plants is common among the elderly attended at the primary health centres of Puente Alto; - It is fundamental to know the plant species used by the population to guide their rational and safe use, considering benefits, adverse effects, and drug interactions.
53	Integration into Primary Care	- Belief in therapeutic effect: 96.2% of professionals believe in the therapeutic effect of medicinal plants, but do not prescribe them; - Knowledge of the National Policy on Integrative and Complementary Practices (PNPIC): 65.6% of professionals know the PNPIC; - Knowledge about the presence of herbal products in the National List of Essential Medicines (RENAME): 85.4% of professionals are unaware of the presence of herbal products in the RENAME; - Origin of knowledge about medicinal plants: 93% of professionals acquired knowledge about medicinal plants through family; - Association between belief in therapeutic effect and family use: a significant difference was observed between professionals who believe in the therapeutic effect of plants and those who use medicinal plants in their families.	- Although most professionals believe in the therapeutic effect of medicinal plants, the majority do not prescribe them; - Knowledge about the PNPIC and the presence of herbal medicines in the RENAME is limited among professionals; - The origin of knowledge about medicinal plants is predominantly familial, indicating the importance of traditional knowledge; - There is a need for training for health professionals to effectively integrate phytotherapy practices into primary healthcare.

6. Discussion

The results presented in Table 1 show the use of phytotherapy in various clinical, population, and geographical contexts, also revealing the scope of phytotherapy practice and its implications for human health, demonstrating its application in the treatment of different diseases and the importance that phytotherapy has for people who use the health system ³⁵.

Firstly, with the results obtained, it is verified that phytotherapy is an ancient practice ^{20,24} and crosses different phases of the life cycle: from paediatrics ⁴², through pregnancy and the puerperium ^{43,44}, up to the elderly population ⁵². This evidence strengthens the culturally embedded nature of phytotherapy, transmitted between generations and practised in domestic contexts as well as in health systems. This transmission between generations

refers to what is called popular phytotherapy, often transmitted orally, or traditional phytotherapy, which often has written records²⁸.

The motivation for the use of phytotherapy appears in several studies and aspects such as accessibility, low cost, cultural tradition, and the belief in safety are mentioned^{42,44,52}. The perception that plants are "natural and harmless" is dangerous, as shown by the results of Muñoz Balbontín *et al.*⁴³, there are associations between certain herbal medicines and obstetric risks, highlighting the idea that the use of phytotherapy without adequate follow-up can lead to serious consequences, hence the importance of the presence of a phytotherapist in the health system, who is qualified to promote health and prevent illness, assess the patient's state of health, as well as identify patterns of imbalance and apply specific criteria of phytotherapy³⁶.

In terms of clinical conditions, the findings reveal that phytotherapy is used and studied in acute illnesses, such as bronchitis⁴⁶, in chronic conditions, such as T2DM⁴⁸⁻⁵⁰, and breast cancer^{8,47}. The analysis thus shows that the search for phytotherapy is due, on the one hand, to reducing dependence on conventional drugs to avoid side effects or unnecessary antibiotic use, and on the other, to therapeutic complementarity, as in the case of chronic diseases like T2DM or oncological diseases like breast cancer, where patients seek greater control over their health and well-being.

Although there are some herbal products with proven efficacy and potential for evidence-based integration^{45,48}, the results showed that gaps still exist: lack of standardisation of doses, variable quality of preparations, and the need for more clinical trials that attest to safety^{46,52}. If, on the one hand, the literature recognises the therapeutic potential of phytotherapy in various conditions, capable of bringing benefits to human health, critical barriers persist that limit its integration into health systems³⁴.

Another aspect that is worth mentioning is the relationship between patients and health professionals, as some studies reveal a lack of communication between these two parties, with patients not informing doctors about the use of herbal products⁵⁰ and health professionals, despite recognising the efficacy of phytotherapy, the majority still do not prescribe it^{33,53}. What emerges from these results is the compromise of safety and the possibility of integrating phytotherapy and conventional therapies. This is explained in the study by Asare *et al.*⁵¹, where it was found that there is great acceptance of phytotherapy, but the lack of training and regulation is visible, which creates obstacles to the safe clinical practice of this ancient therapy.

In summary, the results highlighted three main themes associated with the use of phytotherapy and its benefits for human health: the cultural and social value of phytotherapy, present in different populations; the great therapeutic potential of phytotherapy in various areas and clinical conditions (T2DM, gastrointestinal disorders, bronchitis), but which still require more studies for safe use, both by health professionals and by patients; challenges for the integration of phytotherapy into health systems, namely the need for professional training, clear regulation, research, and reinforcement of patient-doctor communication.

Despite its benefits for human health, phytotherapy continues to face scientific, regulatory, and communicational barriers that need to be overcome so that its use is safe, effective, and integrated into healthcare.

7. Conclusion

The NLR allowed us to confirm that phytotherapy, as an ancient therapeutic practice of TCM, has strong cultural and social acceptance, being used in different phases of the life cycle and in various clinical conditions. The analysed studies highlight important therapeutic benefits, particularly in glycaemic and lipid control, in the case of T2DM, in the improvement of gastrointestinal, respiratory, and oncological symptoms (fewer side effects), as well as in supporting the general well-being of patients.

However, some challenges still persist for the practice and use of phytotherapy that compromise its integration into healthcare: absence of standardisation in doses and preparations, the need for more research to measure efficacy and safety, lack of regulation and training among health professionals, which, in the absence thereof, the presence of phytotherapists or TCM practitioners with phytotherapy training in health services is advocated for teamwork with health professionals.

Credit author statement: Conceptualization: E.S.C. and L.S.S.; Investigation: E.S.C. and L.S.S.; Writing, reviewing and editing: E.S.C. and L.S.S. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding: This research did not receive any specific grant from funding agencies in the public, commercial, or not-for-profit sectors.

Conflict of Interest: The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest.

Institutional Review Board Statement: Not applicable.

Informed Consent Statement: Not applicable.

Data Availability Statement: The original contributions presented in this study are included in the article. Further inquiries can be directed to the corresponding author.

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